

Profile the Displaced Electorate in Tigray Region of Ethiopia

Violence and the fear of violence are the principal sources of internal displacement in Tigray Region, Ethiopia. The roots of the current conflict can be traced to Fighting has ravaged northern Ethiopia since early November, 2020 when the government opened a military offensive against the ruling faction in the region of Tigray, starting a conflict that has caused thousands of deaths and widespread destruction, displaced significant number of people, and sent tens of thousands of refugees into neighboring Sudan. Federal Government ordered the offensive on Nov. 4, 2020. It is not yet estimated that the conflict cost the lives of how many Ethiopian.¹

From 11 December — 14 January 2021, the Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) deployed its Emergency Site Assessment to capture internal displacement related to the Northern Ethiopia Crisis. This multi sectoral location assessment assesses the number of internally displaced persons (IDPs) and collects basic information on the multi sectoral needs of IDPs at site level. In this second round, 131,590 IDPs (30,383 households) were found to be displaced across 39 sites in Tigray, Amhara and Afar regions. 91,046 IDPs (20,530 households) were found in Tigray region, 6,453 IDPs (3,533 households) in Amhara region and 34,091 IDPs (6,320 households) in Afar region. ²

Electoral law and Legal Framework in Tigray, Ethiopia

Ethiopia has a majoritarian first-past-the-post electoral system where members of the House of People's Representatives are elected on the basis of the majority of votes cast in single-member constituencies. In terms of the constitution Ethiopia has a bicameral parliamentary system; the House of People's Representatives (HPR) and the House of the Federation. Members of the HPR are elected for five year terms on the basis of universal suffrage by direct elections held by secret ballot. The Prime Minister is elected from among the members of the HPR.

The House of the Federation (HF) is the upper house and is composed of representatives of “Nations, Nationalities and Peoples”. Each Nation, Nationality and People is represented by at least one member, with each Nation or Nationality represented by one additional

representative per each one million of its population. Members of the HF are chosen by their respective Regional Councils. Alternatively, the Constitution provides for the Regional Councils to have direct elections to the upper house. This option has never been exercised and there is no legislation at regional level providing for direct elections of representatives of the HF. The two federal level houses combine to choose the President of the Federation who is the Head of State. The President has mainly honorary powers and serves a six year term. Elections for the Regional Councils of the nine regions are also conducted under a majoritarian system. These constituencies are multi-mandate. The National Electoral Board of Ethiopia (NEBE) conducts all government elections including the upcoming special election of Tigray.

The law provides for the establishment of polling stations at locations suitable for security. Ethiopian electoral law provides for the election of five observers for each polling station. And the Ethiopian citizen who is above 18 years old on the date of registration and the residence of the place for more than 6 months can vote by showing his residence ID or by bring 3 witness that he was living there.⁴

Each polling station has three staff and a Chief Officer (the presiding officer). The Presiding Officer is responsible for all voting day activities at his or her polling station. They are assisted by the other staff that supports the voting process. The Presiding Officer also has the responsibility of security at the polling station. No one can come within a 500 metre radius of the polling station if they carry a weapon, are drunk or are disturbing the peace in any way. The Presiding Officer determines whether they require police to assist them in ensuring security of voters and can police assistance through the electoral commission offices.

Representatives from the media are permitted to be in the polling stations on condition that they present their credentials and do not interfere with the voting process. Each polling station must be clearly marked and each stage of the voting process identified through placards or tags. Voting hours are from 6h00 – 18h00. Before voters enter the polling station the Presiding Officer takes them through a briefing on the voting process. He/she waits until a group of voters is gathered and gives these briefings throughout Election Day. The briefing includes an explanation of the ballot papers and an explanation of who is contesting the

elections without showing any favouritism for or bias against the candidates or parties. The briefing also contains information on how a ballot should be marked and what constitutes a spoiled ballot.

People who are not allowed to vote are those:

- without an electors card and whose name is not on the voters' roll,
- who are not willing to have their thumb inked, and
- Whose thumb is already inked.

At the end of the voting process, at 18h00 the gate of the polling station must be closed. People who are at the gate and in the queue at the time of closing will be allowed to cast their vote if they meet all the legal requirements for voting. Election wardens are stationed at the gate to ensure that no further people try and enter the area. After the last voter has cast his or her vote the ballot box/es are sealed with a special seal in front of all the observers and party and candidate representatives the tag number of the padlock of the ballot box is recorded by the election officers, observers and party and candidates' representatives.³

Obstacles, Responses, and Timelines in for special election in Tigray, Ethiopia

Ethiopia has experience incorporating IDPs into recent electoral processes which while happen in June 5, 2021, these events will be for Metekle, Ethiopia. this experience have to contributed to confidence-building for the upcoming special election of Tigray, Ethiopia. Virtually all IDPs form Tigray expressed an abiding and deep mistrust of the national electoral system, believing it was biased against Tigray Ethnic interests. The challenge for election organizers is to ensure that the historical perception of bias is not reinforced, and that the outcome genuinely reflects the will of the people, including IDPs. Deliberate attempts to manipulate the election results or technical and administrative problems that undermine popular confidence in the outcome will further alienate the Tigray who is affiliated with former party called TPLF. IDP voting raises special logistical problems that must be addressed early and in a transparent fashion if the program is to contribute to national reconciliation. The balance of this section identifies core issues confronting election organizers.

The other main obstacle Tigray, Ethiopia is plagued by insecurity. As heavy fighting continues to restrict humanitarian operations across parts of Tigray, people are facing an extremely dire humanitarian situation. Clashes continue to be reported in Central, Eastern, North Western, South Eastern and Southern Zones, where social services have reportedly collapsed, according to partners on the ground. A vast majority of health centres have been vandalized, destroyed or burned, and many health personnel have not been paid and are reportedly being threatened by armed actors, further delaying their return to work. Ongoing looting of health facilities, including in Southern Tigray, is hindering the health response, as partners are discouraged from providing medical supplies. People with chronic diseases and pregnant women are particularly affected, as they are unable to access emergency medical services during curfew hours, causing preventable deaths and delivery complications. Universities across Tigray have reportedly been extensively looted, while at least two have been destroyed by fire or bombs.

Basic services, including communications, electricity and banking, remain disrupted across much of Tigray. Approximately 4.5 million people living in rural areas and major towns in North Western Zone have had no power or communications for more than four months. Lack of communications in most areas are adding significant challenges to the delivery and monitoring of life-saving assistance.

In Western Tigray, partners report that tens of thousands of people have been displaced from the area allegedly on ethnic grounds. Since November 2020, the Western Tigray Zone has been under de facto control of Amhara regional authorities, during which there have been reports of ethnically motivated violence and forced displacement. Since February, thousands of residents in Western Tigray have fled the Zone amid reports of extrajudicial killings, arbitrary detentions, and disappearances of people, particularly young men. As of 8 March, more than 45,000 people have been registered in Shire, with an influx of about 1,500 people every day. The newly displaced, who arrive in dire conditions, have reported that some people remain stranded on the way due to lack of transportation from Tekeze River to Shire and have very limited humanitarian assistance. In Shire, aid workers have

started delivering some food, shelter, wash and health assistance, and stressed the very urgent need to provide additional relief to the new arrivals, particularly shelter and non-food items. Humanitarian access and response in Western Zone is currently only possible through Amhara Region.

Aid workers continue to receive reports of attacks on civilians and civilian infrastructure in Central, North Western and South Eastern zones, including house-to-house searches accompanied by indiscriminate, extrajudicial killings. Gender-based violence remains widespread, according to the latest Emergency Coordination Centre meeting on 5 March, and humanitarian actors are still unable to measure the full extent of the situation, particularly in rural areas due to limited access. With government social protection, security and judicial systems not functioning, survivors of human rights abuses are receiving inadequate assistance. International actors, including the World Bank, continue to underscore the importance of safeguarding the rights of all people in Ethiopia. Multiple human rights organizations published, on 9 March, a joint open letter to H.E. Ms. Linda Thomas-Greenfield, Permanent Representative of the US to the UN in New York, calling for a prioritization of the crisis in Tigray at the UN Security Council, including mobilizing an appropriate diplomatic response.

With many areas of Tigray not having received vital assistance since the conflict started four months ago, the rising needs have vastly outstripped the preliminary response plan that was developed by the humanitarian community in the first weeks of the conflict. Now, partners are increasingly able to access hundreds of thousands of people in Tigray who are in desperate need, and to move more supplies and personnel into the region. The 2021 Humanitarian Needs Overview launched by the humanitarian community on 5 March estimates that about 4.5 million people are currently in need of humanitarian assistance in Tigray, of whom 3.5 million people are in accessible and partially accessible areas. The humanitarian community will continue to update this figure as more assessments become possible in the Region. ⁵

Cost projection for special election in Tigray, Ethiopia

The special election costs estimate formula uses the prior election registered voters and increases that number by an additional 10%. That amount is then multiplied by a low and high per voter cost estimate. An estimated cost to include a measure into the Sample Ballot Pamphlet is added if applicable. Election costs for participating jurisdictions are calculated using a cost allocation methodology. The election billing is calculated by adding all election related costs, allocating the overall costs by number of voters and polling places, and adding any unique costs such as sample ballot information for measures, candidates' statements, maps, and signature verification. The costs include:

- **Labor** – The Registrar of Voters' employees charge their time to election specific job codes for each election; therefore, actual hours and wages are charged to the election. In addition, benefits and indirect costs are charged on total wages.
- **Services and Supplies** – The services and supplies that support operations are inspector supply box, voting booths, official ballots, poll officer operations, phone bank operations, early voting, outreach operations, tally center, sample ballot pamphlets, candidate filing, vote-by-mail, and postage.

It takes three to four months after an election to receive all final invoices and calculate the overall cost and cost allocation for each election.

Identifying supporting organization & Establish a Consensus for special election in Tigray, Ethiopia

Donors should ensure that there continues support to this special election as of the general election of Ethiopia in 2021. Support to the electoral program is linked to to protect IDP civil and political rights. Significant donor resources are expected to support key elements of the electoral process. However, no specific programs are yet in place to address the unique needs of the IDPs. While One donor should take the lead on supporting the IDP dimension to the elections. • Donors should coordinate their work on the relationship between peace-building and CSO development in the run-up to the elections. Specialized election and democracy

sensitization information programs will be required that address the core concerns of the IDPs. Donors should support long-term and intensive domestic and international election observation and monitoring. International monitors should be coordinated to ensure sufficient personnel are deployed to the northern districts and can access the IDP camps. The monitoring needs to be long-term, in order to ensure transparency during the campaign period.

The consensus phase should be linked to the ongoing negotiations between the opposition party in Tigray Ethiopia and the Federal Government. Currently Tigray is led by correlation government form majority of the opposition party in Tigray. While the initial consultations focused on immediate security issues, it is hoped the talks will lead to a sustained dialog on achieving a resolution to the conflict. If regular meetings resume, voting rights should be placed on the agenda in the context of discussions regarding human rights protections. While the nature of any political solution is impossible to predict, placing the issue of voting rights squarely on the negotiating agenda could help build a consensus on how to overcome the legacy of mistrust and suspicion that fuels the conflict with TPLF in 2020. In addition, discussion of these issues offers both sides (Federal government of Ethiopia, Tigray regional opposition party) the chance of making confidence building proposals that could facilitate the broader dialog on a permanent solution.

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Reading Material

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